

Book proposal¹

Connective memory and heritage on social media

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1. Book Description

Introduction

How can social media interactions with heritage and the past provide a key to understanding the construction of contemporary identities and attitudes? What are the actual communicative mechanisms that allow banal nationalism, xenophobia, authoritarianism, pseudo-history, and misinformation to thrive on social media platforms? How do capital “I” identities (national, political) manifested in social media interactions intersect with small “i”, identities, preferences, and attitudes towards social and cultural issues? What might be an effective theoretical and methodological approach to representing and analysing social media conversations, connecting how the past is remembered with contemporary attitudes and identities? Questions such as these motivate this book proposal.

Key takeaway

Based on a national case study involving systematic, multifocal analysis of a corpus of ca. 30,000 Facebook conversations and Instagram posts and over 60 interviews with mnemonic actors, the proposed volume demonstrates how the circulation of stories, symbols and metaphors, and the distribution of semiotic agency within a nexus involving heritage and the past, institutions and grassroots communities, and conversations on social media, act as powerful mechanisms for the construction of contemporary identities and attitudes towards the past, the present, and the future.

¹ The proposed volume is based on research conducted as part of “Connective digital memory in borderlands: a mixed-methods study of cultural identity, heritage communication and digital curation on social networks”. The Connective project is funded by the European Social Fund under grant agreement 09.3.3-LMT-K-712-17-0027 with the Research Council of Lithuania (LMTLT). The proposal was submitted to an international academic publisher in November 2023 and is awaiting peer review. This document presents parts of the proposal suitable for public dissemination.

Subject, narrative arc, and research methods

The planned volume presents evidence-based, multi-disciplinary, collaborative research on heritage- and identity-related interactions on social media. It aims to be closer to a multi-authored monograph than to a traditional edited volume of independent contributions. It introduces a theorisation of heritage-related social media interaction as *cultural-semiotic nexus* and proposes a methodological framework for the pragmatic analysis of repertoires of small stories, symbols, deep metaphors, and discourse constructs emerging from social media conversations (posts, comments, reactions) centred on aspects of the often difficult – dissonant, traumatic, subaltern – heritage and the past, and interviews with users active in such conversations. Drawing from its authors' diverse expertise in information, communication and media studies, heritage and museum studies, history, informatics, linguistics, and philosophy, it offers a panorama of focal investigations on the most relevant phenomena represented in a corpus of social media conversations and interviews with mnemonic actors, and their implications on communication theory and social media scholarship. Building on these focal investigations, it advances a theorisation and analysis of how semiotic agency circulates between social media messages, users, algorithmic affordances of social media platforms, and references to events, people, and aspects of heritage and the past, shape the construction of contemporary identities and attitudes between diverse, and often dissonant, interacting groups of users. It also reflects on the philosophical presuppositions and implications of these empirical investigations for communication theory. The proposed volume draws extensively from an evidence-based, multifaceted case study of social media encounters with heritage and the past in contemporary Lithuania.

The story told in the 14 chapters of the volume starts with presenting an argument why the study is needed and what it entails, based on an overview of prior scholarship on connective memory and heritage on social media, and of the the cultural-historical context and particularities of the national case study it is based on (Chapter 1). Then, an examination of what is needed to represent adequately processes of meaning-making in social media memory interactions leads to the elaboration of *cultural-semiotic nexus theory* as an appropriate representation and analysis framework (Chapter 2), which is applied to establish a repertoire of small stories, symbols (also icons, and indexical signs), deep metaphors, and discourse constructs occurring in the corpus of ca. 30,000 conversations on the often contested heritage and history of Lithuania on social media (Chapter 3). This holistic overview sets the stage for an examination of particular case studies of post-memory and identity construction on Lithuanian social media: how childhood in the late Soviet period (Chapter 4) and the youth subcultures and challenges of the 1990s (Chapter 5) are remembered, what is the post-memory of the WWII Polish Home Army partisans in Lithuania (Chapter 6), how Russian Lithuanians self-identify relying on conceptions of the past (Chapter 7), and how invented traditions and ethnographic performance shape creative ethnicity among Lithuanians

(Chapter 8). The story then shifts to conflicts and contestations on contemporary Lithuanian social media: the troubled memories of events related to the resistance and double occupation by the Nazis and Soviets from 1939 to 1953 (Chapter 9), the “monument wars” raging against public monuments and memory institutions focused on historical figures from the Soviet era (Chapter 10), conflicts around the use of the “foreign” letters w, q and x in Lithuanian passports (Chapter 11), and the difficulties and complexities of remembering and silencing of the Roma Holocaust (Chapter 12). Building on these perspectives, the volume then zooms out to show how the cultural-semiotic nexus of stories and diverse post-memories of heritage and the past shapes the construction of contemporary attitudes and futures (Chapter 13), and how it lends support to moderate constructivist communication theory, asserting that semiotic collectives on social media may be conceived as mediated meaning-making figurations determined in part only by technological media affordances (Chapter 14). The following diagram outlines the conceptual structure of the volume.

The volume is the result of multifaceted, evidence-based empirical investigation. It proposes a shared ontological and methodological framework, based on an original theorisation of social media memory practice as *cultural-semiotic nexus*, a formal model and practical method for corpus constitution, data representation and primary (descriptive) analysis, and a shared

glossary of sensitising concepts and objectives. It presents analyses and interpretations of evidence from a corpus of ca. 30,000 Facebook conversations and Instagram posts, supplemented by associated metadata, sequences of included comments, replies and reactions, and author information, and indexed by topic. Data were collected in two data collection campaigns covering the period 2016-2023, through a systematic query-based approach using a taxonomy of 78 topics selected to best represent the thematic range of heritage- and history related social media conversations. Building on a digital humanities approach, data on social media conversations, authors, messages, and their referents from the past were represented as a knowledge graph in a Neo4J database and imported to the MaxQDA qualitative content analysis package for further coding, annotation, and lexical analysis. The corpus was enriched by over 60 interviews with mnemonic actors active in heritage- and history-related conversations on social media. Approaches used in different chapters include corpus linguistics methods, narrative analysis, critical discourse analysis, metaphor analysis, visual methods, qualitative content analysis, and social network analysis.

Why this book matters

The powerful yet problematic role of social media platforms in shaping affiliative communities, senses of self, and attitudes towards others, scientific knowledge, social and cultural values, democratic ideas, and cultural norms has become painfully visible in the last decade. Disinformation campaigns on social media by external state actors have been used to foment internal divisions and subvert democratic norms, while hate speech against Jews, Muslims, immigrants, and more generally ‘others’, often propagates on social media. Anti-rationalist and pseudo-science ideas about the COVID-19 pandemic, climate change and other issues also get amplified on social media platforms. Many of these phenomena weaponize aspects of heritage and the past, and there are well-attested connections between communities and conversations discussing historical events and aspects of cultural identity, with contemporary conflicts about society, politics, and knowledge. This situation is acutely felt in countries belonging to the Eastern borderlands of Europe, which have become a prime target for disinformation campaigns, and where there are high stakes involving public attitudes towards the European idea and the European Union, national identity, ethnolinguistic minorities, democratic norms, human rights, and values.

To account for this problematic situation, the proposed volume **sheds light on the cultural-semiotic mechanisms governing heritage-laden meaning-making and collective agency on social media**. It does so not in the abstract, or eclectically, but through the systematic empirical investigation of a large-scale national case study, based on evidence from Lithuanian social media and heritage practices. Drawing from an analysis of an extensive corpus of empirical evidence, it investigates the actual semiotic resources and mechanisms – the repertoires of salient stories, symbols and metaphors, the nexus of communicative actors,

referents from the past, and semiotic collectives – involved in activating aspects of heritage and the past in social media conversations related to contemporary identities, attitudes, and ideas. It thus provides researchers, policy makers, public institutions, NGOs, activists, and mnemonic actors beyond the national and regional context with useful knowledge on what makes certain social media conversations more efficacious than others, and how negative phenomena such as hate speech, pseudo-history and misinformation can be countered. It also points to diagnostic indicators on how specific references to heritage and the past offer insights on genealogies of meaning, invisible stakeholders and norms, and much-needed awareness that interpretations about the past are constructed, plural, and accountable to critical evaluation and judgment.

The volume also **contributes to theoretical and methodological scholarship on heritage and connective digital memory**. It does so by introducing *cultural-semiotic nexus theory*, a pragmatic ontological and methodological framework suitable for the conceptual representation, analysis and interpretation of heritage interactions and connective memory work on social media. The framework builds on a synthesis of Yuri Lotman's semiosphere theory and Alfred Gell's anthropological theory of the art nexus to connect social media practices with specific norms and presuppositions, including the adoption of authorised discourses by invisible stakeholders, and to trace how semiotic agency flows across social media messages, users, and aspects of heritage and the past. It maps the circulation of small stories, symbols, and metaphors, and the use of presupposition, allusion, and wordplay, in social media conversations to identify distinct, yet possibly overlapping, semiotic collectives engaged with social media, sharing different ideas and attitudes towards the past, the present and the future. It thus contributes to the elaboration of a much needed, and currently lacking, systematics of social media memory practice, able to account for both the granular semiotic mechanisms and artefacts of meaning-making, and the agentive process of meaning translation and cross-temporal circulation of agency between past and present objects and people involved in the connective memory nexus of social media.

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Chapter Summaries

PART A: FOUNDATIONS

1. Introduction (Dallas, Kelpšienė & Laužikas)

This introduction starts with an overview the emergent field of studies on heritage, memory and identity on social media, and situates it within traditions, theories and approaches drawn from memory studies (and its contributing disciplines, especially history and political science), museum and heritage studies, Holocaust studies, and communication and media studies, drawing from recent publications of proposed volume authors². In this context, it then presents the motivation, scope, objectives, and overarching research questions of the Connective Digital Memory in the Borderlands project, situating them in the context of the contested past of Lithuania, and related memory, heritage, and identity practices and discourses. It argues for the urgency for further research on how the semiotic uptakes of heritage play into the construction of contemporary identities and attitudes, it establishes on this basis the objectives and scope for the volume, and it presents an overview of remaining chapters.

2. A cultural-semiotic nexus theory of social media memory practice (Dallas & Laužikas)

This chapter starts by introducing the ontological and epistemological challenges facing social media researchers who work on topics related to cultural heritage, memory practices, and the often difficult – contested, traumatic, subaltern – past. Drawing from conceptual frameworks of cultural-historical activity theory, cultural-semiotics, and the anthropology of material culture, and their applications in questions of collective remembering and material and technological agency, and taking into account theorisations of social media platforms as socio-technical infrastructures, it introduces an agentive semiotic approach to the study of cultural practices on social media, which recognises the primacy of narrative, rhetorics, and semiotic collectives in shaping contemporary identities, norms and attitudes. Building on a recent study³, it presents a formal conceptual model, or ontology, of social media communication, suitable to

² Kelpšienė, I., Armakauskaitė, D., Denisenko, V., Kirtiklis, K., Laužikas, R., Stonytė, R., Murinienė, L., & Dallas, C. (2023). Difficult heritage on social network sites: An integrative review. *New Media & Society*, 25(11), 3137–3164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448221122186>; Kirtiklis, K., Laužikas, R., Kelpšienė, I., & Dallas, C. (2023). An ontology of semiotic activity and epistemic figuration of heritage, memory and identity practices on social network sites. *SAGE Open*, 13(3), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231187367>.

³ Kirtiklis et al., *ibid.*

account for the functional structure of social media interactions, and also for semiotic translation between past referents and current communication contexts, as well as between different contemporary semiotic collective (or semiosphere, in Lotman's terms). And, drawing from a recent elaboration of Alfred Gell's art nexus theory by volume authors⁴, it expands it into a *cultural-semiotic nexus theory* able to capture how semiotic agency (the ability to act through communication) flows between authors of social media messages, potential stakeholders and beneficiaries, but also actual expressions in social media messages, and the historical events, people, places, things, and other referents they index. Finally, based on a review of relevant approaches from narrative analysis, critical discourse analysis, and conceptual metaphor analysis, and especially their applications on questions of memory, identity and agency, it introduces the methodological approach adopted by authors for the formal representation and analysis of meaning-making structures in social media interactions.

3. Repertoires of stories, symbols, and metaphors (Kelpšienė, Dallas & Laužikas)

Drawing from the account of the scholarly research and cultural-historical context of the Connective study in chapter 1, and the theoretical framework, conceptual models, and methodological approach introduced in chapter 2, this chapter first presents the systematic case study, based on the construction and analysis of a corpus of conversations on heritage and the past in Lithuanian social media (over 30,000 threads, including over 200,000 messages - posts or comments), as well as over 50 semi-open qualitative interviews with selected social media mnemonic actors. It outlines the schema and main characteristics of this corpus, and illustrates the taxonomy of thematically-structured queries that underlies the evidence-based methodology of appraisal for the corpus, and the processes and outcomes of computer-assisted thematic coding. It also addresses the identification of references to historical actors, events, places, and things (tangible and intangible) in social media references, the representation of structures of propagation and affect in social media conversations, and the elicitation of meaning. Offering a critical introduction of relevant methods drawn from semiotics, narrative analysis, conceptual metaphor analysis and discourse analysis, it then presents an quantitative overview and analysis of a systematic repertoire of small stories, symbols, conceptual metaphors, discourse constructs, and deep semiotic structures underlying the social media conversations in the corpus.

⁴ Laužikas, R., & Dallas, C. (forthcoming). The message is the agent: Nexus and semiosphere in social media communication. In E. Zantides & S. Andreou (Eds.), *Semiotics and Visual Communication IV: Myths of Today*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

PART B: POST-MEMORIES AND IDENTITIES

4. Photographic memories of everyday Soviet life (Stonytė)

This chapter discusses how contemporary social media users in Lithuania engage with the past by sharing old personal photos on social networks. There is a growing trend towards visual storytelling on social networks: by sharing a decades-old photograph, users trigger conversations about the peculiarities of Soviet life, and attempt to create eyewitness narratives from their own personal archives, presenting the photograph as factual evidence. These photographs evoke emotions and memories from other group members, which are shared in the comments, and create a broader discussion about everyday practices in Soviet times. The chapter analyzes the experiences of everyday life in Soviet era as captured in photographs and shared in Facebook groups. Content analysis is used to analyse the images and the public's reactions to the shared content, in order to answer the following questions: What do the photos reveal about people's everyday lives in the Soviet era? What are the dominant themes? Are there ideological/political aspects and symbols in these photos and comments? Which emotions do these photos evoke? It is not only the moment of sharing personal photos that emerges as important from this analysis, but also the selection of which memories are shared on social networks, and which remain hidden.

5. Remembering the shifting identities of 1990s Lithuania (Kelpšienė)

The chapter explores the dynamic interplay between historical memory, cultural transformation, and digital representation in the context of post-Soviet Lithuania, specifically focusing on the digital memory of the transformative 1990s. As Lithuania grappled with the intricate process of rebuilding its political, economic, and cultural foundations, the nation encountered many challenges. The narrative of this period is woven with threads of social tension, political unrest, economic turmoil, hyperinflation, rampant corruption, and criminal activities. Simultaneously, the 1990s saw a rapid influx of Western culture and values, which disrupted and reshaped Lithuania's national identity. As the nation embraced new ideals and influences, it embarked on a complex journey of self-discovery. The chapter critically examines how Lithuanian everyday life and culture during the 1990s are remembered and represented on social networking sites, with a specific focus on Facebook and Instagram to capture the diverse ways in which users engage with and memorialize this transformative period. Central to the exploration are three overarching research questions: How is the Lithuanian 1990s transformation portrayed and perceived within the realm of social network sites? What identities, whether cultural or national, emerged or evolved as a result of this transformative era? How does the resonance of the 1990s period intersect with present-day realities in Lithuania? To address these questions, the chapter adopts a systematic methodological approach based on data collection from Facebook and Instagram

platforms, as well as interviews with platform users. Employing a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods such as content analysis, sentiment analysis, textual and visual analysis, the chapter endeavours to unveil not only the nostalgia and collective memory associated with the 1990s Lithuanian transformation but also the evolving facets of identity and the bridge that connects historical experiences with the contemporary socio-cultural landscape.

6. Polish identity and the Armia Krajowa in public imagination (Bożerocki)

The memory of the Home Army (Armia Krajowa), the Polish nationalist partisan organisation operating in Lithuania during the Second World War, is still relevant today. Although there are almost no witnesses today left to relate first-hand the events of World War II, discussions are ongoing, increasingly so on social media, where various narratives can be formed and propagated. The focus of this chapter is to investigate why the collective memory of the Home Army is not part of the collective identity of Poles living in Lithuania. The research will be based on the hypothesis that this is influenced not only by the dominant Lithuanian national narrative, but also by pro-Soviet propaganda operating through social media. The research presented in the chapter is based on analysis of existing narratives, and content analysis, of thematically-selected conversations on Lithuanian social media from the Connective corpus.

7. Russian speakers' self-identification, and stereotypes about the past (Sushkevych)

This chapter addresses the problem of Russian speakers' identities on the Lithuanian segment of Facebook and V Kontakte. This issue is regarded through the prism of users' purposes, ideas, and attitudes to Lithuania, processes in the country, events and memory work based on the analysis of more than 300 threads and 10 interviews with social media activists within the Connective project. Russian speakers are viewed as constructed identities with different backgrounds, values and stereotypes united by the same means of communication, namely, the Russian language. Their interaction on social media is analyzed through the prism of their direct or indirect coding of both self-conception and reflections of other interlocutors about them. Correspondingly, Russian-speaking constructed identities fall into several categories, namely, positive/supportive, balanced and critical associating this distinction with the processes of acculturation, integration and adaptation or estrangement happening as a result of living or contacting with Lithuania, and its people for some period of time. After such sort of analysis, I reflect on the reasons for such variations in users' views grounding this idea with the change in the societal agreement and stereotypes, which resulted in the creation of new realia after the fall of the USSR. This process was accompanied by a significant shift in the scope, meaning and understanding of the "responsibility" realia in post-Soviet times.

8. Ethnoculture, intangible heritage, and social media communities (Laužikas)

This chapter analyses how intangible heritage and ethnoculture(s) work in contemporary Lithuanian society. The theoretical framework of research is based on three conceptual ideas: (i) the theory of the semiosphere of Yuri Lotman, the founder of the Tartu School of Semiotics; (ii) Hobsbawm's concept of "invented tradition"; (iii) Stern's concept of "creative ethnicity" h. The chapter starts with an overview of the terminology used in Lithuanian SNS and related to intangible heritage (in the UNESCO 2003 Convention sense). The key findings of the research are: (i) ethnoculture in Lithuania operates in four main forms (clusters of communities, semiospheres): people without an interest in ethnoculture and intangible heritage (there are groups of people with no interest in ethnoculture at all; no interest in Lithuanian [ethno]culture); people, interested in ethnoculture and intangible heritage in museum and musealisation sense (archived, musealised intangible heritage); people interested in ethnoculture and intangible heritage in the sense of scenic performance (ethno shows with a clear division between performers and spectators), and living ethnoculture and intangible heritage related people and groups. The ethnoculture as scenic performance dominates in Lithuania. There is not much of a living, functioning and important to creating identity ethnoculture-based phenomena. Each interest in ethnoculture is linked to a central (semiospheric) idea: musealisation, performativity (performative arts) and continuity of tradition. They also have emerging "creolised spaces" (e.g. museum education creolises museums with scenic performance, while leisure ethnoculture creolises scenic performance and living ethnoculture). Invented traditions dominated during the Soviet period and creative ethnicity was destroyed at this time. As a result, when Lithuania restored its independence and the state stopped being a formative apparatus, a large niche. Communities are trying to fill the niche by creative ethnicity. During the Soviet era, the natural development of ethnic culture was interrupted. On the one hand, some traditions (e.g. religious) were not practised in the public sphere. In contrast, others were artificially modified according to the needs of Soviet ideology and the Soviet system. Thus, in this situation, many intangible heritage items, whose natural evolution did not take place, have difficulty finding a place in the present social/cultural/economic contexts.

PART D: CONFLICTS AND CONTESTATIONS

9. Information conflicts over occupations, war, and resistance (Denisenko)

Based on an analysis of social media conversations on significant historical events such Lithuania regaining Vilnius (1939), World War II (1939-1945), the Molotov-Ribbentrop pact (1939), the first Soviet occupation of Lithuania (1940) and the June uprising (June 1941), the Nazi occupation (1941-1944), the Holocaust in Lithuania (especially in 1941), the anti-Soviet resistance movement of the Forest Brothers (1944-1953), and the history of Soviet oppression

and exile (especially in 1941 and 1949), this chapter situates the memory of such events as a manifestation of topical „living history“ practice, but also as a field of information conflict in the contemporary setting, amenable to dissonant interpretations, manipulation and disinformation, especially among representatives of different ethnic groups of Lithuanian society. To do so, it analyses stories about mentioned events from the Connective corpus, supplemented by interview data, focusing on identifying divergent discourses and interpretations about the same events across different “texts”, including pictures and comments.

10. Dissonant heritages and monument wars (Armakauskaitė)

This chapter analyses the discussions on Facebook related to heritage sites, urban areas, public places and institutions of memory, which are subject to mixed interpretations, as well as the participants of these discussions. The resumption of military action by Russia on the territory of Ukraine on 24 February 2022 marks a turning point in the evaluation of Soviet-era heritage, which led to intense debates on Facebook as well as public actions, dedicated to de-sovietisation of urban spaces. The theoretical basis of the research is developed using Y. Lotman's concept of cultural semiotics, which states that no sign system has an inherent mechanism that allows it to function in isolation and the comparative typology of memory activists developed by Y. Gutman and J. Wüstenberg. Based on the theoretical framework, 3 main research questions are identified: (a) what are the characteristics of the typology of memory activists in the discussions about disputed heritage on Facebook? (b) how does the content of discussions on dissonant heritage on Facebook change as the context changes? (c) what are the main motives and narratives of the participants in the discussions and how do they correlate with the types of participants in the discussions? The study revealed the following key findings: (a) after 24th February 2022, the context of semiosphere changed significantly and has influenced a change of attitude towards the dissonant heritage through the acquisition of new knowledge and viewpoints; (b) there was also a particularly significant change in the valuation of Soviet-era heritage objects as attributes of a still-continuing past – a continuation of Russia's imperialist policy today, represented by Soviet-era monument; (c) discussions on Facebook are dominated by social network users who apply the warrior mode of action and take on the roles of victims, heroes and resisters, and engaged actors while pragmatists tend to opt for the pluralist model of action, which has become unpopular after February 2022; and, (d) the role of engaged actors - warriors in Facebook posts and discussions - is often occupied by politicians, who have the power to initiate and carry out changes in the urban fabric of the city.

11. Fighting over three letters on Lithuanian passports (Murinienė)

Ties between the Lithuanian language and Lithuanian identity are very tight and have so far seemed immovable. After Lithuania regained its independence, Lithuanian was declared the state language. Various legal acts related to language regulated the fields of usage of the Lithuanian language. One of them is the names and surnames of national minorities, which had to be transcribed into Lithuanian according to approximate pronunciation, and thus presented in the passports of Lithuanian citizens. The essential question, which has been raised several times since the 1990s, is whether the three Latin letters w, q and x can be used as a system in the passports of Lithuanian citizens. In January 2022, the Seimas of the Republic of Lithuania adopted a historic decision to write names and surnames in passports by retaining the Latin letters of the original, or transliterating them in Latin, if the person's surname is not in the Latin alphabet. This law was confirmed by the President of the Republic and came into force. However, society is not united on this issue. Its fragmentation is particularly evident on social networks. Public attitudes range from liberal to extreme radical. This chapter addresses the need to conduct a study that would allow to determine the public's attitude towards national identity, the links between identity and language, attitudinal transformations, tolerance, and rejection. It asks the following questions: How does society's assessment of identity issues reveal itself in free natural unrestricted language? How important is the Lithuanian language (and specifically the three Latin letters w, q, and x) for Lithuanian identity? How liberal / radical is that assessment? How does that assessment relate to national minorities and non-ethnolinguistic Lithuanians? To address these questions, it applies Martin and White's *Language of evaluation* methodology to analyse a collection of linguistic data on Facebook and Instagram appraised by using thematic keywords (related to the three letters theme), as well as interviews with social media users active in relevant conversations.

12. Contestations and silences on the Holocaust among the Lithuanian Roma (Latvytė)

This chapter analyses difficulties faced by the Roma community to commemorate its traumatic past, and the challenges faced by the community in overcoming the stigmas entrenched in society against the community. This case study focuses on the memory of the Paneriai mass extermination site in situ, and seeks to highlight the importance of the site for raising not only the Roma community's memory awareness but the rest of the society as well. The research was conducted with the aim to identify the communicative narratives on the Roma Holocaust in Lithuania, and to try to search for semiotic behaviour while also creating creolization spaces as an opportunity for a dialogue and a way of promoting empathy in society.

PART D: SOCIAL MEDIA, MEMORY & IDENTITY

13. A nexus of constructed pasts, affiliative collectives, and imagined futures (Dallas & Laužikas)

Building on the approaches, findings and interpretations of chapters 3-12, this chapter applies an agentic semiotic framework, and related representation and analysis models and methods, to demonstrate how the use of stories, symbols, metaphors, and discursive and pragmatic strategies such as presupposition, allusion, wordplay and irony applied on diverse memory fields – from the post-memory of anti-Soviet partisans to the Holocaust, from late Soviet nostalgia to the memory of the ‘singing revolution’ and the youth subcultures of independent Lithuania, and from the monument wars of the 2010s to revisionist, anti-establishment and anti-liberal contemporary phenomena – are entangled with the agency, norms and communicative codes of different semiotic collectives, and with the algorithmic logic of social media platforms, to form what is termed a *cultural-semiotic nexus* with significant effects in the propagation of prevalent beliefs on the past, affects and attitudes towards the present, and imaginings about the future. The chapter applies the cultural-semiotic nexus theory and analysis framework introduced earlier to identify how specific deep narratives, small stories, metaphors, existential and normative presuppositions across the whole Connective corpus of social media conversations, illuminated by a qualitative content analysis of interviews with selected social media mnemonic actors, construct figured worlds and affiliative identities bringing together social media users into culturally and politically relevant semiotic collectives, with potential impact on norms and attitudes towards Europe, democratic values. Revealing the crucial role of perceptions of the past, semiotic functions, and algorithmic agency for shaping the circulation of agency between human and non-human agents – poised to be even more consequential with the rapid advances in the capabilities and general access to generative AI and large language models - the chapter concludes by offering a speculative vision for a radical rehauling of social media interactions and citizen education that could reclaim the initial promise of social media to act as deliberative contact zones rather than as symbolic battlefields, and for the past to serve as a beacon for an informed, democratic future based on reason and human values rather than pseudo-history, tribalism, and hatred of others.

14. Communicating the past on Lithuanian social media: two faces of constructivism (Kirtiklis)

This chapter asks whether the analysis of social media exchanges concerning aspects of heritage might not only shed light on the ongoing debate between transmission and constitutive approaches of communication, but also take into account less known and rather

rarely discussed alternatives, such as the radical constructivist perspective on communication. Drawing from a critical analysis of studies included in this volume, and accounting for the very process of communicative interaction on social network sites *qua* communication, it engages in a critique of both the transmission model and of the radical constructivist model, concluding that neither meets necessary conditions as an appropriate framework to account for communication on social media. It concludes, instead, that the most fecund approach is presented by moderate social constructivism, defining communication as meaning making, and based on intersubjectivity, and the encounters of different perspectives. In this light, the conversation threads and, surely also, the thematically defined collectives created within Lithuanian social media may be understood as mediated meaning making figurations (even if temporary and unstable), enabled by the technological environment, yet not confined to it.

3. Editor and Author Info

Editor / chapter author bios

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